

Supporting Information 1 – Data Collection

Fossil Locality Data

Fossil Data - Summary Table

Table S1. Fossil Site Location, Date and Faunal List Summary.

Name	Lat (N)	Long (E)	Coordinates Estimated	Location Citation	MIS	Age Citation	Absolute	Indirect	Faunal List Source
Miesenheim I	50.4833	7.4500		Von Koenigswald & Heinrich, 1999	13	Van Kolfschoten & Turner, 1996; Maul et al., 2000; Haidle & Pawlik, 2010		+	Van Kolfschoten & Turner, 1996
Kärlich Gb	50.4666	7.4666		Von Koenigswald & Heinrich, 1999	15-13	Van Kolfschoten & Turner, 1996		+	Van Kolfschoten & Turner, 1996
Mosbach 2	50.0666	8.2666		Von Koenigswald & Heinrich, 1999	13	Maul et al., 2000; Van der Made & Grube, 2010		+	Von Koenigswald & Heinrich, 1999
Mauer	49.3333	8.8166		Von Koenigswald & Heinrich, 1999	15-13	Schreve & Bridgland, 2002; Van der Made & Grube, 2010; Wagner et al., 2010; Wagner et al., 2011	+	+	Wagner et al., 2011
Husarenhof 4	49.9833	9.1666		Von Koenigswald & Heinrich, 1999	15-13	Maul & Heinrich, 2007		+	Von Koenigswald & Heinrich, 1999

Erpfinden 1	48.3666	9.2000	Von Koenigswald & Heinrich, 1999	15-13	Ufrecht et al., 2003; Maul & Heinrich, 2007		+	Von Koenigswald & Heinrich, 1999	
Erpfinden 3	48.3666	9.2000	Von Koenigswald & Heinrich, 1999	15-13	Maul & Heinrich, 2007		+	Von Koenigswald & Heinrich, 1999	
Sudmer Berg-2	51.9166	10.4833	Von Koenigswald & Heinrich, 1999	15-13	Maul & Heinrich, 2007; Wagner et al., 2011		+	Von Koenigswald & Heinrich, 1999	
Kärlich H	50.4666	7.4666	Von Koenigswald & Heinrich, 1999	11	Van Kolfshoten & Turner, 1996; Van Asperen, 2012		+	Van Kolfshoten & Turner, 1996	
Kärlich-Seeufer	50.4666	7.4666	Von Koenigswald & Heinrich, 1999	11	Gaudzinski et al., 1996		+	Von Koenigswald & Heinrich, 1999	
Heppenloch	48.5333	9.5167	Von Koenigswald & Heinrich, 1999	11	Kahlke et al., 2011; Van Asperen, 2012; Rivals & Ziegler, 2018		+	Von Koenigswald & Heinrich, 1999	
Petersbuch 1	48.9667	11.1833	Von Koenigswald & Heinrich, 1999	11	Von Koenigswald, 1970; Van Kolfshoten, 2014		+	Von Koenigswald & Heinrich, 1999	
Bilzingsleben II	51.2833	11.0666	Von Koenigswald & Heinrich, 1999	11	Schwarcz et al., 1988; Maul et al., 2000; Stephan, 2000; Schreve & Bridgland, 2002; Haidle & Pawlik, 2010; Van der Made & Grube, 2010; Müller & Pasda, 2011; Van Asperen, 2012; Daniel & Frenzel, 2023		+	+	Von Koenigswald & Heinrich, 1999
Neede	52.1333	6.6000	Von Koenigswald & Heinrich, 1999	11	Meijer, 2002; Van Kolfshoten, 2014		+	Von Koenigswald & Heinrich, 1999	
Ariendorf 1	50.5333	7.2833	Von Koenigswald & Heinrich, 1999	11	Haidle & Pawlik, 2010		+	+	Von Koenigswald & Heinrich, 1999

Stuttgart (bad Cannstatt) Bunker	48.8167	9.2167	Von Koenigswald & Heinrich, 1999	11	Schatz, 1997; Van Asperen, 2012	+	Von Koenigswald & Heinrich, 1999	
Steinheim (Antiquus- Schotter)	48.9667	9.2833	Von Koenigswald & Heinrich, 1999	11	Rivals & Ziegler, 2018; Van Asperen, 2012; Van Asperen, 2013; Schreve & Bridgland, 2002; Kahlke et al., 2011;	+	Van Asperen, 2013	
Schöningen 13 I	52.1833	11.0333	Von Koenigswald & Heinrich, 1999	11	Van Kolfschoten, 2014	+	Van Kolfschoten, 2014	
Schöningen 12 B	52.1833	11.0333	Von Koenigswald & Heinrich, 1999	9	Van Kolfschoten, 2014	+	Van Kolfschoten, 2014	
Schöningen 13 II-1	52.1833	11.0333	Von Koenigswald & Heinrich, 1999	9	Van Kolfschoten, 2014	+	Van Kolfschoten, 2014	
Schöningen 13 II-4	52.1833	11.0333	Von Koenigswald & Heinrich, 1999	9	Van Asperen, 2012; Van Kolfschoten, 2014	+	Van Kolfschoten, 2014	
Schönebeck-Welsleben	52.0000	11.6333	Von Koenigswald & Heinrich, 1999	9	Van Kolfschoten, 2014; Von Koenigswald et al., 2019	+	Von Koenigswald & Heinrich, 1999	
Wageningen – Fransche Kamp II	51.9833	5.7000	Von Koenigswald & Heinrich, 1999	7	Van Kolfschoten, 1991; Van Kolfschoten, 2014	+	Von Koenigswald & Heinrich, 1999; Van Kolfschoten, 2001	
Rhemen-Leccius de Ridder	51.9667	5.5833	Von Koenigswald & Heinrich, 1999	7	Von Koenigswald & Heinrich, 1999; Meijer, 2002	+	Von Koenigswald & Heinrich, 1999	
Maastricht-Belvédère 3 & 4	50.8833	5.7000	Von Koenigswald & Heinrich, 1999	7	Van Kolfschoten et al., 1993; Van Kolfschoten, 2014	+	+	Von Koenigswald & Heinrich, 1999
Weimar-Ehringsdorf (Upper Travertine)	50.9500	11.3500	Von Koenigswald & Heinrich, 1999	7	Schwarcz et al., 1988; Schreve & Bridgland, 2002; Haidle & Pawlik, 2010; Van Kolfschoten, 2014	+	+	Von Koenigswald & Heinrich, 1999

Weimar-Ehringsdorf (Lower Travertine)	50.9500	11.3500		Von Koenigswald & Heinrich, 1999	7	Schreve & Bridgland, 2002; Haidle & Pawlik, 2010; Van Kolfschoten, 2014	+	+	Von Koenigswald & Heinrich, 1999
Tönchesberg I (1A)	50.3667	7.3833		Von Koenigswald & Heinrich, 1999	5	Gaudzinski et al., 1995; Van Kolfschoten, 2000; Van Asperen, 2012		+	Von Koenigswald & Heinrich, 1999
Erkenbrechtsweiler	48.5500	9.5333		Von Koenigswald & Heinrich, 1999	5	Von Koenigswald & Schmidt-Kittler, 1972; Von Koenigswald & Heinrich, 1999		+	Von Koenigswald & Heinrich, 1999
Hunas M	49.5000	11.5500		Von Koenigswald & Heinrich, 1999	5	Rosendahl et al., 2011		+	Von Koenigswald & Heinrich, 1999
Neumark-Nord (Interglacial Sediments)	51.3333	11.8667		Von Koenigswald & Heinrich, 1999	5	Van Kolfschoten, 2000		+	Von Koenigswald & Heinrich, 1999
Rabutz	51.4333	12.1833		Von Koenigswald & Heinrich, 1999	5	Van Kolfschoten, 2000		+	Von Koenigswald & Heinrich, 1999
Grabschütz	51.4667	12.2833		Von Koenigswald & Heinrich, 1999	5	Van Kolfschoten, 2000		+	Von Koenigswald & Heinrich, 1999
Northern Upper Rhine Basement	49.7000	8.4667	+	Von Koenigswald & Heinrich, 1999	5	Von Koenigswald, 1988; Von Koenigswald & Menger, 1997; Von Koenigswald & Heinrich, 1999; Von Koenigswald & Menger, 2002		+	Von Koenigswald & Heinrich, 1999
Wannenköpfe-West	50.3639	7.4108		Kalthoff et al., 2007	5	Kalthoff et al., 2007		+	Kalthoff et al., 2007
Stuttgart-Untertürkheim (Lower Travertine)	48.7500	9.2333		Von Koenigswald & Heinrich, 1999	5	Van Kolfschoten, 2000	+	+	Von Koenigswald & Heinrich, 1999

Steinheim an der Murr (Eemian fauna)	48.9667	9.2833	Von Koenigswald & Heinrich, 1999	5	Von Koenigswald & Heinrich, 1999; Van Kolfshoten, 2000		+	Von Koenigswald & Heinrich, 1999
Neddenaverbergen	52.8667	9.3667	Von Koenigswald & Heinrich, 1999	5	Von Koenigswald & Heinrich, 1999		+	Von Koenigswald & Heinrich, 1999
Lehringen	52.8667	9.3833	Von Koenigswald & Heinrich, 1999	5	Van Kolfshoten, 2000		+	Von Koenigswald & Heinrich, 1999
Burgtonna (Travetine Layer)	51.0667	10.7333	Von Koenigswald & Heinrich, 1999	5	Van Kolfshoten, 2000; Schreve & Bridgland, 2002	+	+	Von Koenigswald & Heinrich, 1999
Weimar (Belvédère Allee) Stadtgebiet	50.9833	11.3333	Von Koenigswald & Heinrich, 1999	5	Van Kolfshoten, 2000; Van Asperen, 2012		+	Von Koenigswald & Heinrich, 1999
Taubach (Thüringen)	50.9500	11.3833	Von Koenigswald & Heinrich, 1999	5	Van Kolfshoten, 2000; Van Asperen, 2012	+	+	Von Koenigswald & Heinrich, 1999
Gröbern	51.7000	12.4500	Von Koenigswald & Heinrich, 1999	5	Van Kolfshoten, 2000		+	Von Koenigswald & Heinrich, 1999
Schönfeld (Brandenburg)	51.8167	13.8833	Von Koenigswald & Heinrich, 1999	5	Van Kolfshoten, 2000		+	Von Koenigswald & Heinrich, 1999
Wallertheim A/B	49.8355	8.0514	Conard, 1999	5	Van Kolfshoten, 2000; Van Asperen, 2012		+	Conard et al., 1995; Gaudzinski, 1995
Hunas I	49.5000	11.5500	Von Koenigswald & Heinrich, 1999	3	Rosendahl et al., 2011		+	Von Koenigswald & Heinrich, 1999
Hunas H	49.5000	11.5500	Von Koenigswald & Heinrich, 1999	3	Rosendahl et al., 2011		+	Von Koenigswald & Heinrich, 1999
Hunas G3	49.5000	11.5500	Von Koenigswald & Heinrich, 1999	3	Rosendahl et al., 2011		+	Von Koenigswald & Heinrich, 1999

Hunas G2	49.5000	11.5500		Von Koenigswald & Heinrich, 1999	3	Rosendahl et al., 2011		+	Von Koenigswald & Heinrich, 1999
Grotte de la Belle-Roche	50.4811	5.6128		Di Modica & Pirson, 2016	13	Di Modica & Pirson, 2016		+	Cordy, 1993
Mesvin IV	50.4225	3.9693		Di Modica & Pirson, 2016	7	Cahen et al., 1983; Di Modica & Pirson, 2016		+	Van Neer, 1986
Zemst A	50.9972	4.3958		Germonprè et al., 1993	5	Germonprè et al., 1993			Germonprè, 2003
Zemst IIB	50.9972	4.3958		Germonprè et al., 1993	5	Germonprè et al., 1993		+	Germonprè, 2003
Grotte Scladina	50.4853	5.0264		Blain et al., 2014	5	Bastin et al., 1986; Blain et al., 2014			Bastin et al., 1986
Caverne Marie-Jeanne (6-4)	50.2167	4.7850		López-García et al., 2017	3	López-García et al., 2017		+	López-García et al., 2017
Grotte Walou (CI)	50.5930	5.6989		Stewart & Parfitt, 2011	3	Stewart & Parfitt, 2011			Stewart & Parfitt, 2011
Trou Magrite (2, 3)	50.2221	4.9127		Gautier et al., 1997	3	Gautier et al., 1997; Straus et al., 2023		+	Gautier et al., 1997
Abbeville-Carrière Carpentier (White Marl/Unit 4)	50.1067	1.8472		Antoine et al., 2016	15-13	Antoine et al., 2016; Brugal et al., 2020		+	Antoine et al., 2016
Grotte de L'Escaie at Saint-Estève Janson	43.6828	5.3920	+	N/A	15-13	Palombo & Valli, 2004; Ghezzi et al., 2014			Palombo & Valli, 2004
Caune de l'Arago Ensemble II - (H)	42.8394	2.7550		López-García et al., 2021	13	Falguères et al., 2015; Moigne et al., 2006		+	Montuire & Desclaux, 1997; Moigne et al., 2006

Caune de l'Arago Ensemble II - (I)	42.8394	2.7550		López-García et al., 2021	13	Moigne et al., 2006	+		Montuire & Desclaux, 1997; Moigne et al., 2006
Caune de l'Arago Ensemble II - (J)	42.8394	2.7550		López-García et al., 2021	13	Moigne et al., 2006	+		Montuire & Desclaux, 1997; Moigne et al., 2006
Terra Amata	43.6977	7.2893	+	Moigne et al., 2016	11	Valensi, 2001; Valensi et al., 2011		+	Valensi et al., 2011
La Celle	48.3924	2.8340	+	Limondin-Lozouet et al., 2010	11	Limondin-Lozouet et al., 2006; Limondin-Lozouet et al., 2010	+	+	Limondin-Lozouet et al., 2006
Cagny-la-Garenne II	49.8562	2.3407	+	Antoine, 1990	11	Auguste, 2009, Limondin-Lozouet et al., 2010		+	Auguste, 2009
Pradayrol - Séronie-Vivien borehole (Layer 4)	44.6202	1.6774		Bardeau & Belgodere, 2009; Marquet & Séronie-Vivien, 2016	11	Marquet & Séronie-Vivien, 2016	+	+	Marquet & Séronie-Vivien, 2016
Pradayrol - Séronie-Vivien borehole (Layer 2B)	44.6202	1.6774		Bardeau & Belgodere, 2009; Marquet & Séronie-Vivien, 2016	9	Marquet & Séronie-Vivien, 2016	+	+	Marquet & Séronie-Vivien, 2016
Orgnac 3 (Layer 7)	44.2944	4.4202		Lewis, 2011	9	Bahain et al., 2022	+	+	Lewis, 2011
Orgnac 3 (Layer 6)	44.2944	4.4202		Lewis, 2011	9	Bahain et al., 2022	+	+	Lewis, 2011
Cagny-l'Épinette (Layer I)	49.8547	2.3156	+	Tuffreau et al., 1995	9	Tuffreau et al., 1995; Tuffreau, 2007; Malinsky-Buller, 2015	+	+	Tuffreau et al., 1995
Lunel-Viel I	43.6842	4.0800	+	Brugal et al., 2021	9	Van der Made, 2010; Brugal et al., 2021		+	Brugal et al., 2021

Soucy (1-4)	48.2476	3.2968	+	Lhomme, 2007	9	Lhomme, 2007; Malinsky-Buller, 2015	+	+	Lhomme, 2007
Ranville	49.2200	-0.2600	+	Depaepe, 2009	7	Auguste, 2009	+	+	Auguste, 2009
Tourville-la-Rivière (D1)	49.3288	1.1061	+	N/A	7	Balescu et al., 1997; Antoine et al., 2007	+	+	Auguste, 2009
Biache - Saint-Vaast	50.3000	2.9333		Guipert et al., 2011	7	Auguste, 2009; Guipert et al., 2011	+	+	Auguste, 2009
Montmaurin karst - La Niche (Layer C)	43.2167	0.6000		Vialet et al., 2018	7	Crégut-Bonnoure et al., 2010b; Vialet et al., 2018		+	Crégut-Bonnoure et al., 2010b
Coudoulous I (FU IV+V)	44.4778	1.6639		Fernandez et al., 2021	7	Fernandez et al., 2021		+	Fernandez et al., 2021
Coudoulous I (FU III)	44.4778	1.6639		Fernandez et al., 2021	7	Fernandez et al., 2021		+	Fernandez et al., 2021
Payre (F)	44.7316	4.7363		Richard et al., 2021	7	Moncel & Condemi, 2007; Valladas et al., 2008	+	+	Desclaux & Hazzazi, 2008; Ecker et al., 2013
Payre (G)	44.7316	4.7363		Richard et al., 2021	7	Moncel & Condemi, 2007; Valladas et al., 2008	+	+	Desclaux & Hazzazi, 2008; Ecker et al., 2013
Montières-Les-Amiens	49.9050	2.2590	+	Tuffreau et al., 1981	7	Auguste, 2009		+	Auguste, 2009
Moru (lower terrace of the Oise)	49.3133	2.6834	+	Bordes, 1957; Freidin, 1977; Blanchet & Fitte, 1978	7	Auguste, 2009		+	Auguste, 2009
Bau de l'Aubesier (K1)	44.0431	5.3364	+	Pop, 2022	7	Carmignani et al., 2017		+	Auguste, 2009

Piégu (layer G)	48.5969	2.5522		Danukalova et al., 2015	7	Auguste, 2009; Bahain et al., 2012	+	+	Bahain et al., 2012; Danukalova et al., 2015
Bau de l'Aubesier (4)	44.0431	5.3364	+	Pop, 2022	5	Carmignani & Soressi, 2023	+	+	Palombo & Valli, 2004
Mont-Dol	48.5710	-1.7660	+	Auguste, 2009	5	Auguste, 2009		+	Auguste, 2009
Payre (D)	44.7316	4.7363		Richard et al., 2021	5	Moncel & Condemi, 2007; Valladas et al., 2008	+	+	Desclaux & Hazzazi, 2008; Ecker et al., 2013
Grotte des Ramandils (Unit II)	43.0330	2.9830		Markova & Puzachenko, 2018	5	Rusch et al., 2019	+	+	Rusch et al., 2019
le Grand Abri aux Puces	44.2331	5.1391	+	Lewis, 2011	5	Slimak et al., 2010		+	Slimak et al., 2010
Abri Moula XV	44.8532	4.8204	+	Saos et al., 2014; Willmes et al., 2016	5	Defleur & Desclaux, 2019	+	+	Crégut-Bonnoure et al., 2010a
Abri Moula XIV	44.8532	4.8204	+	Saos et al., 2014; Willmes et al., 2016	5	Defleur & Desclaux, 2019	+	+	Crégut-Bonnoure et al., 2010a
Grotte des Barasses II - Lower	44.5119	4.3700		Richard et al., 2021	5	Richard et al., 2015; Daujeard et al., 2019	+	+	Daujeard et al., 2019
Pech de l'Azé IV (Layer 8)	44.8333	1.2333		Bordes, 1978	5	Niven, 2013; Jankowski, 2018	+	+	Niven, 2013
Abri Moula XI/X	44.8532	4.8204	+	Saos et al., 2014; Willmes et al., 2016	5	Defleur & Desclaux, 2019	+	+	Montuire & Desclaux, 1997;
Pech de l'Azé IV (Layer 6A/6B)	44.8333	1.2333		Bordes, 1978	5	Niven, 2013; Jankowski, 2018	+	+	Niven, 2013

Caours	50.1300	1.8780		Markova & Puzachenko, 2018	5	Schreve et al., 2007; Markova & Puzachenko, 2018	+	+	Schreve et al., 2007; Markova & Puzachenko, 2018
Lazaret (CII, CIII)	43.6900	7.2950		Markova & Puzachenko, 2018	5	Abdessadok et al., 1997; Markova & Puzachenko, 2018		+	Montuire & Descalux, 1997; Palombo & Valli, 2004; Markova & Puzachenko, 2018
Orgnac 3 (Layer 5a)	44.3170	4.4500		Markova & Puzachenko, 2018	5	Markova & Puzachenko, 2018			Markova & Puzachenko, 2018
Abri-des-Pêcheurs (ensemble 1)	44.4080	4.2060		Markova & Puzachenko, 2018	5	Markova & Puzachenko, 2018			Markova & Puzachenko, 2018
Grotte du Portel (L, K)	43.0270	1.5360		Markova & Puzachenko, 2018	5	Markova & Puzachenko, 2018			Markova & Puzachenko, 2018
Coudoulous I (plancher sup.)	44.4690	1.6900		Markova & Puzachenko, 2018	5	Markova & Puzachenko, 2018			Markova & Puzachenko, 2018
Grotte Vaufrey (IV)	44.8000	1.2000		Markova & Puzachenko, 2018	5	Markova & Puzachenko, 2018			Markova & Puzachenko, 2018
Grotte des Barasses II - Upper	44.5119	4.3700		Richard et al., 2021	3	Richard et al., 2015; Daujeard et al., 2019	+	+	Daujeard et al., 2019
Hénin-Sur-Cojeul	50.2190	2.8340	+	Antoine, 1993; Marcy et al., 1993; Auguste, 2009;	3	Marcy et al., 1993; Auguste, 2009	+	+	Auguste, 2009
Hortus 2	43.7905	3.8312		Williams et al., 2023	3	Barroso-Ruiz, 2006; Williams et al., 2023		+	Montuire & Descalux, 1997
Pech de l'Azé I (Layer 4)	44.8333	1.2333		Bordes, 1978	3	Soressi et al., 2007; Rendu, 2010		+	Rendu, 2010

Pech de l'Azé I (Layer 6)	44.8333	1.2333		Bordes, 1978	3	Soressi et al., 2007; Williams et al., 2023	+	+	Render, 2010
Pech de l'Azé I (Layer 7)	44.8333	1.2333		Bordes, 1978	3	Soressi et al., 2007;	+	+	Render, 2010
Les Pradelles (4A, 4B, 5)	45.7414	0.4330		Mussini, 2011	3	Royer et al., 2013		+	Royer et al., 2013
Pradayrol (Ensemble 2 - Layers I/II, II)	44.6202	1.6774	+	Bardeau & Belgodere, 2009; Marquet & Séronie-Vivien, 2016	3	Villeneuve et al., 2019		+	Villeneuve et al., 2019
Westbury Cave (Breccia - Units 12/11/10)	51.2505	-2.7062		Polly & Stringer, 2011	15- 13	Polly & Stringer, 2011; Parfit & Preece, 2022		+	Polly & Stringer, 2011
Westbury Cave (12)	51.2505	-2.7062		Polly & Stringer, 2011	15- 13	Polly & Stringer, 2011; Parfit & Preece, 2022		+	Polly & Stringer, 2011
Westbury Cave (15/1)	51.2505	-2.7062		Polly & Stringer, 2011	15- 13	Polly & Stringer, 2011; Parfit & Preece, 2022		+	Polly & Stringer, 2011
Westbury Cave (15/2)	51.2505	-2.7062		Polly & Stringer, 2011	15- 13	Polly & Stringer, 2011; Parfit & Preece, 2022		+	Polly & Stringer, 2011
Happisburgh Site 1	52.8194	1.5441		Lewis et al., 2019	13	Polly & Stringer, 2011; Candy et al., 2015; Lewis et al., 2019 (see Gibbard et al. (2019) for discussion)		+	Polly & Stringer, 2011
Boxgrove (Interglacial Deposits)	50.8705	-0.6939		Polly & Stringer, 2011	13	Roberts & Parfit, 1999; Polly & Stringer, 2011; Candy et al., 2015		+	Polly & Stringer, 2011
High Lodge	52.3489	0.5519	+	Polly & Stringer, 2011	13	Polly & Stringer, 2011; Candy et al., 2015		+	Polly & Stringer, 2011

Hoxne	52.3475	1.1942	+	Schreve, 1998	11	Schreve, 1998	+	Schreve, 1998
Barnfield Pit	51.4456	0.2989	+	Schreve, 1998	11	Schreve, 1998	+	Schreve, 1998
Dierden's Pit	51.4503	0.2947	+	Schreve, 1998	11	Schreve, 1998	+	Schreve, 1998
Clacton-On-Sea/Jaywick-Sands	51.7866	1.1528	+	Schreve, 1998	11	Schreve, 1998	+	Schreve, 1998
Barnham	52.3747	0.7539	+	Schreve, 1998	11	Schreve, 1998	+	Schreve, 1998
Beeches Pit	52.3161	0.6372	+	Schreve, 1998	11	Schreve, 1998	+	Schreve, 1998
Copford	51.8822	0.8500	+	Schreve, 1998	11	Schreve, 1998	+	Schreve, 1998
Hitchin Deposits	51.9400	-0.2653	+	Schreve, 1998	11	Schreve, 1998	+	Schreve, 1998
Hicks Brickyard	52.5447	-0.2458	+	Schreve, 1998	11	Schreve, 1998	+	Schreve, 1998
Purfleet Chalk Pits	51.4849	0.2601	+	Schreve, 1998	9	Schreve, 1998	+	Schreve, 1998
Grays Thurrock	51.4792	0.3350	+	Schreve, 1998	9	Schreve, 1998	+	Schreve, 1998
Cudmore Grove	51.7921	0.9961	+	Schreve, 1998	9	Schreve, 1998	+	Schreve, 1998

Belhus Park	51.5064	0.2672	+	Schreve, 1998	9	Schreve, 1998	+	Schreve, 1998	
Avon Terrace 5	52.1156	-2.0908	+	Schreve, 1998	9	Schreve, 1998	+	Schreve, 1998	
Wolvercote Brick Pit	51.7914	-1.2786	+	Schreve, 1998	9	Schreve, 1998	+	Schreve, 1998	
Barling	51.5697	0.7928	+	Schreve, 1998	9	Schreve, 1998	+	Schreve, 1998	
Sandy Lane Quarry	51.5044	0.2369	+	Schreve, 1998	7	Schreve, 1998	+	Schreve, 1998	
Uphall Pit	51.5522	0.0705	+	Schreve, 1998	7	Schreve, 1998	+	Schreve, 1998	
Itteringham Gravel Pit	52.8300	1.1744	+	Schreve, 1998	7	Schreve, 1998	+	Schreve, 1998	
Lion Pit	51.4814	0.3006	+	Schreve, 1998	7	Schreve, 1998	+	Schreve, 1998	
Ebbsfleet Valley	51.4378	0.3228	+	Schreve, 1998	7	Schreve, 1998	+	+	Schreve, 1998
Jordans Pit	52.0428	0.7158	+	Schreve, 1998	7	Schreve, 1998	+	+	Schreve, 1998
Stoke Bone Bed	52.0472	1.1522	+	Schreve, 1998	7	Schreve, 1998	+	Schreve, 1998	
Stutton	51.9544	1.1283	+	Schreve, 1998	7	Schreve, 1998	+	Schreve, 1998	

Harkstead	51.9564	1.1881	+	Schreve, 1998	7	Schreve, 1998	+	Schreve, 1998
College Farm (3, 2)	51.8217	-0.6483	+	Schreve, 1998	7	Schreve, 1998	+	Schreve, 1998
Dixs pit	51.7461	-1.4025	+	Schreve, 1998	7	Schreve, 1998	+	Schreve, 1998
Lexden Brick Pit	51.8917	0.8739	+	Schreve, 1998	7	Schreve, 1998	+	Schreve, 1998
Selsey/West Wittering	50.7272	-0.7808	+	Schreve, 1998	7	Schreve, 1998	+	Schreve, 1998
Stone Point	50.7839	-1.3525	+	Schreve, 1998	7	Schreve, 1998	+	Schreve, 1998
Bielsbeck Farm	53.8297	-0.6925	+	Schreve, 1998	7	Schreve, 1998	+	Schreve, 1998
Stoke Goldington	52.1358	-0.7558	+	Schreve, 1998	7	Schreve, 1998	+	Schreve, 1998
Upper Strensham	52.0561	-2.1406	+	Schreve, 1998	7	Schreve, 1998	+	Schreve, 1998
Crayford Brickearths	51.4614	0.1831	+	Schreve, 1998	7	Schreve, 1998	+	Schreve, 1998
Great Yeldham	52.0122	0.5594	+	Schreve, 1998	7	Schreve, 1998	+	Schreve, 1998
Sible Heddingham	51.9803	0.5978	+	Schreve, 1998	7	Schreve, 1998	+	Schreve, 1998

Tornewton Cave (Otter Stratum)	50.4942	-3.6689	+	Schreve, 1998	7	Schreve, 1998	+	+	Schreve, 1998
Bleadon Cave	51.3186	-2.9189	+	Schreve, 1998	7	Schreve, 1998		+	Schreve, 1998
Hutton Cave	51.3186	-2.9189	+	Schreve, 1998	7	Schreve, 1998		+	Schreve, 1998
Oreston Caves	50.3656	-4.1083	+	Schreve, 1998	7	Schreve, 1998		+	Schreve, 1998
Pontnewydd Cave (Lower Breccia/Intermediate Complex)	53.2269	-3.4769	+	Schreve, 1998	7	Schreve, 1998		+	Schreve, 1998
Burtle Beds	51.0983	-2.8797	+	Currant, 2004	5	Currant, 2004		+	Currant, 2004
Barrington Beds	52.1233	0.0167	+	Gibbard & Stuart, 1975	5	Gibbard & Stuart, 1975; Currant & Jacobi, 2001		+	Gibbard & Stuart, 1975
Swanton Morley	52.7341	0.9897	+	Coxon et al., 1980	5	Coxon et al., 1980		+	Coxon et al., 1980
Joint Mitnor Cave	50.4853	-3.7711	+	Currant & Jacobi, 2001	5	Currant & Jacobi, 2001		+	Currant & Jacobi, 2001
Bacon Hole (I/H/G)	51.5628	-4.0783	+	Currant & Jacobi, 2001	5	Currant & Jacobi, 2001	+	+	Currant & Jacobi, 2001
Banwell Bone Cave	51.3253	-2.8861	+	Currant & Jacobi, 2001	5	Currant & Jacobi, 2011; Stevens & Reade, 2021	+	+	Currant & Jacobi, 2011

Eastbourne	50.7919	0.2894	+	Jennings & Smyth, 1987	5	Jennings & Smyth, 1987; Sutcliffe, 1995	+	Jennings & Smyth, 1987
Trafalgar Square	50.7919	0.2894	+	Preece, 1999	5	Sutcliffe, 1995; Currant & Jacobi, 2011	+	Franks, 1960
Tornewton (Hyaena Stratum)	50.4942	-3.6689	+	Schreve, 1998	5	Schreve, 1998; Campbell et al., 1998	+	Campbell et al., 1998; Markova & Puzachenko, 2018
Victoria Cave (Lower Cave Earth)	54.1270	-2.2640		Markova & Puzachenko, 2018	5	Gascoyne et al., 1981; Lundberg et al., 2010	+	O'Connor & Lord, 2013; Markova & Puzachenko, 2018
Kirkdale Cave	54.2619	-0.9614	+	Boylan, 1981	5	McFarlane & Ford, 1997	+	Boylan, 1981
Raygill Fissure (Unit 3)	53.9093	-2.0672	+	Davis, 1886	5	O'Connor & Lord, 2013	+	O'Connor & Lord, 2013
Stump Cross Caverns	54.0669	-1.8647	+	Baker et al., 1996	5	Sutcliffe, 1995; Lundberg et al., 2020	+	Lundberg et al., 2020
Picken's Hole (Unit 5)	51.2908	-2.8669	+	Scott, 2018	5	Scott, 2018	+	Scott, 2018
Lynford Quarry	52.5208	0.6892	+	Boismier et al., 2003	3	Schreve, 2006	+	Schreve, 2006
Picken's Hole (Unit 3)	51.2908	-2.8669	+	Scott, 2018	3	Scott, 2018	+	Scott, 2018
Pontnewydd Cave (Upper Breccia)	53.2269	-3.4769	+	Schreve, 1998	3	Dinnis et al., 2016; Walker, 2018	+	Walker, 2018
Pin Hole (Lower Cave Earth)	53.2625	-1.2017	+	Currant & Jacobi, 2001	3	Currant & Jacobi, 2001	+	Currant & Jacobi, 2001

Robin Hood Cave	53.2627	-1.2001	+	Charles et al., 1994	3	Currant & Jacobi, 2001; Dinnis et al., 2016	+	+	Dawkins, 1876; Currant & Jacobi, 2001
Coygan Cave (Inner/Outer Chamber/Hyaena Den)	51.7547	-4.4869	+	Aldhouse-Green et al., 1995	3	Aldhouse-Green et al., 1995; Jacobi et al., 2009; Jacobi & Higham, 2011	+	+	Aldhouse-Green et al., 1995
Whitemoor Haye Quarry	52.7122	-1.7447	+	Schreve et al., 2012	3	Schreve et al., 2012	+	+	Schreve et al., 2012
Glaston	52.5968	-0.6818	+	Cooper et al., 2012	3	Cooper et al., 2012	+	+	Cooper et al., 2012
Cathole Cave (Trench B)	51.5900	-4.1122	+	Walkers et al., 2014	3	Walkers et al., 2014	+	+	Walkers et al., 2014
Wookey Hole (Hyaena Den)	51.2289	-2.6711	+	Currant, 2004	3	Currant, 2004		+	Currant, 2004
Sanford Hill	51.3278	-2.8239	+	Currant, 2004	3	Currant, 2004		+	Currant, 2004
Kents Cavern (Bed 4)	50.4675	-3.5025	+	Campbell et al., 1998	3	Campbell et al., 1998; Dinnis et al., 2016	+	+	Campbell et al., 1998

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Guild Assignments

Guild Assignment - Summary Table

Table S2. Taxa guild assignment [A (arboreal) or T (terrestrial)] and trophic [P (primary consumer), or S (secondary consumer)].

Taxa	Extinct	Synonym Citation	Size	Locomotor	Trophic	Size Justification	Locomotor Justification	Trophic Justification
<i>Asoriculus sp.</i>	1		S	T	S	Phylogenetically close to <i>Soriculus nigrescens</i> (Bover et al., 2018), which is a known small, 17.6-gram (Chen et al., 2023) fossorial insectivore (Wilson & Mittermeier, 2018).		
<i>Crocidura sp.</i>			S	T	S	Assignment follows most common assignments to <i>Crocidura</i> .		
<i>Crocidura ex gr. russula-leucodon</i>			S	T	S	Assignment follows <i>C. russula</i> and <i>C. leucodon</i> .		
<i>Crocidura leucodon</i>			S	T	S	Assigned by Louys et al. (2015).		
<i>Crocidura robusta</i>	1		S	T	S	Assignment follows <i>C. russula</i> based on morphological similarity (Rofes & Cuenca-Bescós, 2011).		
<i>Crocidura russula</i>			S	T	S	Assigned by Louys et al. (2015).		
<i>Crocidura suaveolens</i>			S	T	S	Assigned by Louys et al. (2015).		
<i>Neomys sp.</i>			S	T	S	Assignment follows <i>N. anomalus</i> , and <i>N. fodiens</i> .		
<i>Neomys anomalus</i>			S	T	S	Assigned by Louys et al. (2015).		
<i>Neomys browni</i>	1		S	T	S	Assignment follows <i>N. anomalus</i> and <i>N. fodiens</i> based on morphological similarity (Rzebik-Kowalska, 2008; Rzebik-Kowalska & Rekovets, 2016).		
<i>Neomys fodiens</i>			S	T	S	Assigned by Louys et al. (2015).		
<i>Neomys intermedius</i>	1		S	T	S	Assignment follows <i>N. anomalus</i> and <i>N. fodiens</i> based on morphological similarity (Rzebik-Kowalska, 2008; Rzebik-Kowalska & Rekovets, 2016).		

<i>Neomys newtoni</i>	1		S	T	S	Assignment follows <i>N. anomalus</i> and <i>N. fodiens</i> based on morphological similarity (Rzebik-Kowalska, 2008; Rzebik-Kowalska & Rekovets, 2016).
<i>Sorex sp.</i>			S	A	S	Assignment follows most common assignments to <i>Sorex</i> .
<i>Sorex ex gr. araneus-coronatus</i>			S	A	S	Assignment follows <i>S. araneus</i> .
<i>Sorex alpinus</i>			S	A	S	Assigned by Louys et al. (2015).
<i>Sorex araneus</i>			S	A	S	Assigned by Louys et al. (2015).
<i>Sorex caecutiens</i>			S	A	S	Assigned by Louys et al. (2015).
<i>Sorex coronatus</i>			S	T	S	Assigned by Louys et al. (2015).
<i>Sorex minutissimus</i>			S	A	S	Assigned by Louys et al. (2015).
<i>Sorex minutus</i>			S	A	S	Assigned by Louys et al. (2015).
<i>Sorex praealpinus</i>	1		S	A	S	Assignment follows <i>S. alpinus</i> based on morphological similarity (Berto et al., 2022).
<i>Sorex runtonensis</i> (= <i>aranoides/kennardi</i>)	1	Rofes et al., 2016	S	A	S	Assignment follows <i>S. tundrensis</i> based on morphological similarity (Rofes et al., 2016).
<i>Sorex subaraneus</i>	1		S	T	S	Assignment follows <i>S. coronatus</i> based on morphological similarity (Rzebik-Kowalska & Pereswiet-Soltan, 2018).
<i>Sorex (Drepanosorex) sp.</i>	1		S	T	S	Assignment follows <i>S. (D.) savini</i> based on comparisons by Zaitsev & Baryshnikov (2002) and Rofes & Cuenca-Bescós (2013).
<i>Sorex (Drepanosorex) savini</i>	1		S	T	S	Assignment follows <i>Neomys sp.</i> based on ecomorphological similarity (Botka & Mészáros, 2018).
<i>Desmana sp.</i>			S	T	S	Assignment follows most common assignments to <i>Desmana</i> .
<i>Desmana moschata</i>			S	T	S	Assigned by Louys et al. (2015).
<i>Talpa sp.</i>			S	T	S	Assignment follows most common assignments to <i>Talpa</i> .

<i>Talpa europaealis</i>	1	S	T	S	Assignment follows <i>T. romana</i> based on morphological similarity (Popov, 2018).
<i>Talpa europaea</i>		S	T	S	Assigned by Louys et al. (2015).
<i>Talpa minor</i>	1	S	T	S	Assignment follows <i>T. caeca</i> based on morphological similarity (Popov, 2018).
<i>Erinaceus sp.</i>		S	A	S	Assignment follows most common assignments to <i>Erinaceus</i> .
<i>Erinaceus davidi</i>	1	S	A	S	Assignment follows <i>E. europaeus</i> based on morphological similarity (Rzebik-Kowalska, 2013).
<i>Erinaceus europaeus</i>		S	A	S	Assigned by Louys et al. (2015).
<i>Macaca sp.</i>		L	A	S	Assignment follows <i>M. sylvanus</i> .
<i>Macaca sylvanus</i>		L	A	S	9.9–14.5 kg (midpoint = 12.2 kg; Mittermeier et al., 2013). Habitat and activity patterns include adaptation to trees (Mittermeier et al., 2013). Opportunistic feeder with an omnivorous diet (Mittermeier et al., 2013).
Lagomorpha		S	T	P	All members assigned consistently by Louys et al. (2015).
Leporidae		S	T	P	All members assigned consistently by Louys et al. (2015).
<i>Lepus sp.</i>		S	T	P	Assignment follows most common assignments to <i>Lepus</i> .
<i>Lepus ex gr. timidus-capensis</i>		S	T	P	Assignment follows <i>L. timidus</i> and <i>L. capensis</i>
<i>Lepus capensis</i>		S	T	P	Assigned by Louys et al. (2015).
<i>Lepus europaeus</i>		S	T	P	Assigned by Louys et al. (2015).
<i>Lepus praetimidus</i>	1	S	T	P	Assignment follows <i>L. timidus</i> based on morphological similarity (Fostowicz-Frelik & Gasparik, 2006).
<i>Lepus timidus</i>		S	T	P	Assigned by Louys et al. (2015).
<i>Oryctolagus sp.</i>		S	T	P	Assignment follows <i>O. cuniculus</i> .

<i>Oryctolagus cuniculus</i>		S	T	P	Assigned by Louys et al. (2015).
<i>Ochotona sp.</i>		S	T	P	Assignment follows <i>O. pusilla</i> .
<i>Ochotona pusilla</i>		S	T	P	95-270g (Wilson et al., 2016). Spends most of its time within burrows. Locomotion is adapted to dashing to hide under cover of vegetation or rocks (Wilson et al., 2016). Herbivorous (Wilson et al., 2016).
<i>Apodemus sp.</i>		S	A	S	Assignment follows most common assignments to <i>Apodemus</i> .
<i>Apodemus ex gr. sylvaticus-flavicollis</i>		S	A	S	Assignment follows <i>A. sylvaticus</i> and <i>A. flavicollis</i> .
<i>Apodemus coronensis</i>	1	S	A	S	Assignment follows <i>A. maastrichtensis</i> based on morphological (Suárez & Mein, 1998).
<i>Apodemus flavicollis</i>		S	A	S	Assigned by Louys et al. (2015).
<i>Apodemus maastrichtensis</i>	1	S	A	S	Assignment follows <i>A. uralensis</i> and <i>A. agrarius</i> based on morphological similarity (Knittlová & Horáček, 2017).
<i>Apodemus microps</i>	1	S	A	S	Assignment follows <i>A. maastrichtensis</i> based on morphological similarity (Suárez & Mein, 1998).
<i>Apodemus sylvaticus</i>		S	A	S	Assigned by Louys et al. (2015).
<i>Apodemus uralensis</i>		S	A	S	Assigned by Louys et al. (2015).
<i>Eliomys sp.</i>		S	A	S	Assignment follows most common assignments to <i>Eliomys</i> .
<i>Eliomys quercinus</i>		S	A	S	Assigned by Louys et al. (2015).
<i>Glis (=Myoxus) glis</i>	Violani & Zava, 1994	S	A	S	Assigned by Louys et al. (2015).
<i>Hystrix cristata</i>		L	A	S	Assigned by Louys et al. (2015).
<i>Marmota sp.</i>		S	A	S	Assignment follows most common assignments to <i>Marmota</i> .

<i>Marmota marmota</i>		S	A	S	Assigned by Louys et al. (2015).		
<i>Marmota primigenia</i>	1	S	A	S	Assignment follows <i>M. marmota</i> based on morphological similarity (Husson & van der Sluys, 1954; Estraviz-López et al., 2021).		
<i>Allocricetus sp. or Cricetulus sp.</i>		S	T	S	Assignment follows most common assignments to <i>Allocricetus</i> and <i>Cricetulus</i> .		
<i>Allocricetus bursae</i>	1	S	T	S	Assignment follows <i>Cricetulus migratorius</i> based on morphological similarity (Horacek & Lebedová, 2022).		
<i>Arvicola sp.</i>		S	T	P	Assignment follows most common assignments to <i>Arvicola</i> .		
<i>Arvicola ex gr. cantiana-mosbachensis</i>		S	T	P	Assignment follows <i>A. terrestris-cantiana</i> and <i>A. mosbachensis</i> .		
<i>Arvicola ex gr. sapidus-terrestris</i>		S	T	P	Assignment follows <i>A. terrestris-cantiana</i> and <i>A. sapidus</i> .		
<i>Arvicola terrestris-cantiana(=cantianus)</i>	Doukas et al., 2018	S	T	P	Assigned by Louys et al. (2015).		
<i>Arvicola amphibius</i>		S	T	P	80-320g (Wilson et al., 2017).	Moves by walking and running on the ground surface, or through underground tunnels - no mention of arboreal adaptation (Wilson et al., 2017).	Diet predominantly consisted of green plants, tubers and rhizomes (Wilson et al., 2017).
<i>Arvicola mosbachensis</i>	1	S	T	P	Assignment follows <i>A. terrestris</i> based on morphological similarity (Kalthoff et al., 2007).		
<i>Arvicola sapidus</i>		S	T	P	Assigned by Louys et al. (2015).		
<i>Chionomys nivalis</i>		S	T	P	Assigned by Louys et al. (2015).		
<i>Cricetulus migratorius</i>		S	T	S	Assigned by Louys et al. (2015).		
<i>Castor fiber</i>		L	T	P	Assigned by Louys et al. (2015).		
<i>Clethrionomys sp.</i>	Kryštufek et al., 2019	S	A	S	Assignment follows most common assignments to <i>Clethrionomys</i> .		

<i>Clethrionomys (=Myodes) acrorhiza</i>	1	Kryštufek et al., 2019	S	A	S	Assignment follows <i>C. glareolus</i> based on morphological similarity (Kurtén, 2007, p. 213).
<i>Clethrionomys (=Myodes) glareolus</i>		Kryštufek et al., 2019	S	A	S	Assigned by Louys et al. (2015).
<i>Cricetus sp.</i>			S	T	S	Assignment follows most common assignments to <i>Cricetus</i> .
<i>Cricetus cricetus</i> (<i>cricetus/runtonensis/praeglacialis</i>)			S	T	S	Assigned by Louys et al. (2015).
<i>Cricetus major</i>	1		S	T	S	Assignment follows <i>C. cricetus</i> based on morphological similarity (Horacek & Lebedová, 2022).
<i>Dicrostonyx sp.</i>			S	T	P	Assignment follows most common assignments to <i>Dicrostonyx</i> .
<i>Dicrostonyx guielmi</i>	1		S	T	P	Assignment follows <i>D. torquatus</i> based on morphological similarity (Ponomarev & Puzachenko, 2015).
<i>Dicrostonyx torquatus</i>			S	T	P	Assigned by Louys et al. (2015).
<i>Dinaromys bogdanovi</i>			S	A	P	54-99g (Wilson et al., 2017). Shown ability to climb steep habitat, and observed in trees (Wilson et al., 2017). Herbivorous (Wilson et al., 2017).
<i>Lagurus lagurus</i>			S	T	P	Assigned by Louys et al. (2015).
<i>Lemmus sp.</i>			S	T	P	Assignment follows most common assignments to <i>Lemmus</i> .
<i>Lemmus sp. or Myopus sp.</i>			S	T	P	Assignment follows most common assignments to <i>Lemmus</i> and <i>Myopus</i> .
<i>Lemmus lemmus</i>			S	T	P	Assigned by Louys et al. (2015).
<i>Microtus sp.</i>			S	T	P	Assignment follows most common assignments to <i>Myotus</i> .
<i>Microtus ex gr. agrestis-arvalis-arvalinus</i>			S	T	P	Assignment follows <i>M. agrestis</i> and <i>M. arvalis</i> .
<i>Microtus ex gr. malei-oeconomus</i>			S	T	P	Assignment follows <i>M. malei</i> and <i>M. oeconomus</i> .
<i>Microtus agrestis</i>			S	T	P	Assigned by Louys et al. (2015).

<i>Microtus arvalinus</i>	1		S	T	P	Assignment follows <i>M. agrestis</i> and <i>M. arvalis</i> based on morphological and phylogenetic similarity (Maul et al., 2007; Ivanov & Vöröš, 2014).
<i>Microtus arvalis</i>			S	T	P	Assigned by Louys et al. (2015).
<i>Microtus malei</i>	1		S	T	P	Assignment follows <i>M. arvalis</i> based on morphological similarity (Markova, 2006).
<i>Microtus nivalinus</i>	1		S	T	P	Assignment follows <i>M. oeconomus</i> based on phylogenetic similarity (Pazonyi et al., 2018).
<i>Microtus oeconomus</i>			S	T	P	Assigned by Louys et al. (2015).
<i>Microtus problematicus</i>	1		S	T	P	Assignment follows <i>M. arvalis</i> and <i>Arvicola sp.</i> based on morphological similarity (Heller, 1968).
<i>Microtus pyrenaicus</i> (= <i>gerbii/gerbei</i>)		Tougard et al., 2008	S	T	P	Assigned by Louys et al. (2015).
<i>Microtus ratticepoides</i>	1		S	T	P	Assignment follows <i>M. oeconomus</i> based on morphological and phylogenetic similarity (Maul et al., 2007; Maul & Parfitt, 2010).
<i>Microtus (Iberomys) cabrerai</i>			S	T	P	30-78g (Wilson et al., 2017). Active in sites with dense vegetation and uses the habitat to move through it using surface runways - no mention of arboreality (Wilson et al., 2017). Eats primarily vegetation, and rarely eats insects (Wilson et al., 2017).
<i>Microtus (Iberomys) brecciensis</i>	1		S	T	P	Assignment follows <i>M. (I) cabrerai</i> based on morphological similarity (Pita et al., 2014).
<i>Microtus (Terricola) sp.</i>			S	T	P	Assignment follows most common assignments to <i>Microtus (T)</i> .
<i>Microtus (Terricola) arvalidens</i> (= <i>arvaloides</i>)	1	Maul & Parfitt, 2010	S	T	P	Assignment follows <i>M. (T) subterraneus</i> based on morphological and phylogenetic similarity (Maul et al., 2007).
<i>Microtus (Terricola) duodecimcostatus</i>			S	T	P	Assigned by Louys et al. (2015).
<i>Microtus (Terricola) hintoni</i>	1		S	T	P	Assignment follows <i>L. gregalis</i> , <i>L. gregaloides</i> , and <i>L. subterraneus</i> based on morphological and phylogenetic similarity (Maul et al., 2007; Pazonyi et al., 2018; Fadeeva et al., 2022).
<i>Microtus (Terricola) mariaclaudiae</i>	1		S	T	P	Assignment follows <i>M. (T) pyrenaicus</i> based on morphological and phylogenetic similarity (Tougard et al., 2008).

<i>Microtus (Terricola) multiplex</i>			S	T	P	19-29g (Wilson et al., 2017).	Adapted to fossorial locomotion (Wilson et al., 2017).	Consistent primary consumer (Wilson et al., 2017).
<i>Microtus (Terricola) (=Pitymys) subterraneus</i>		Bogdanov et al., 2021	S	T	P		Assigned by Louys et al. (2015).	
<i>Microtus (Terricola) vaufreyi</i>	1		S	T	P		Assignment follows <i>M. (T) subterraneus</i> and <i>M. (T) multiplex</i> based on morphological similarity (Antoñanzas & Bescós, 2002).	
<i>Lasiopodomys (=Microtus/Stenocranius) gregalis</i>		Petrova et al., 2014	S	T	P		Assigned by Louys et al. (2015).	
<i>Lasiopodomys (=Microtus (T)/Stenocranius/Pitymys) gregaloides</i>	1	Petrova et al., 2014	S	T	P		Assignment follows <i>L. gregalis</i> based on morphological and phylogenetic similarity (Maul et al., 2007; Fadeeva et al., 2022).	
<i>Muscardunus sp.</i>			S	A	S		Assignment follows most common assignments to <i>Muscardunus</i> .	
<i>Muscardinus avellanarius</i>			S	A	S		Assigned by Louys et al. (2015).	
<i>Myopus schisticolor</i>			S	T	P		Assigned by Louys et al. (2015).	
<i>Parapodemus coronensis</i>	1		S	A	S		Assignment follows <i>Apodemus microps</i> and <i>Apodemus maastrichtensis</i> based on morphological similarity (Suárez & Mein, 1998).	
<i>Petauria sp.</i>			S	A	S		Assignment follows most common assignments to <i>Petauria</i> .	
<i>Petauria helleri</i>	1		S	A	S		Assignment follows <i>Pteromys volans</i> based on morphological similarity (Wagner et al., 2011).	
<i>Pliomys sp.</i>	1		S	A	P		Assignment follows <i>Dinaromys bogdanovi</i> based on morphological similarity (Chaline, 1977; Chaline et al., 1999; Cuenca-Bescós et al., 2010; Abramson et al., 2021).	
<i>Pliomys coronensis (=lenki)</i>	1	Alfaro-Ibáñez et al., 2024	S	A	P		Assignment follows <i>Dinaromys bogdanovi</i> based on morphological similarity (Chaline, 1977; Chaline et al., 1999; Cuenca-Bescós et al., 2010; Abramson et al., 2021).	
<i>Pliomys chalinei</i>	1		S	A	P		Assignment follows <i>Dinaromys bogdanovi</i> based on morphological similarity (Chaline, 1977; Chaline et al., 1999; Cuenca-Bescós et al., 2010; Abramson et al., 2021).	
<i>Pliomys episcopalis</i>	1		S	A	P		Assignment follows <i>Dinaromys bogdanovi</i> based on morphological similarity (Chaline, 1977; Chaline et al., 1999; Cuenca-Bescós et al., 2010; Abramson et al., 2021).	
<i>Pliomys proavius</i>	1		S	A	P		Assignment follows <i>Dinaromys bogdanovi</i> based on morphological similarity (Chaline, 1977; Chaline et al., 1999; Cuenca-Bescós et al., 2010; Abramson et al., 2021).	
<i>Pliomys progressus</i>	1		S	A	P		Assignment follows <i>Dinaromys bogdanovi</i> based on morphological similarity (Chaline, 1977; Chaline et al., 1999; Cuenca-Bescós et al., 2010; Abramson et al., 2021).	

<i>Prometheomyinae sp.</i>			S	T	P	Assigned by Louys et al. (2015). Assignment is supported by phylogenetic relationship with <i>Prometheomys schaposchnikowi</i> and <i>Dinaromys bogdanovi</i> (Buzan et al., 2008).	
<i>Sciurus sp.</i>			S	A	P	Assignment follows <i>S. vulgaris</i> .	
<i>Sciurus vulgaris</i>			S	A	P	Assigned by Louys et al. (2015).	
<i>Sicista sp.</i>			S	A	S	Assignment follows <i>S. subtilis</i> and <i>S. betulina</i> .	
<i>Sicista ex gr. subtilis-betulina</i>			S	A	S	Assignment follows <i>S. subtilis</i> and <i>S. betulina</i> .	
<i>Sicista betulina</i>			S	A	S	Assigned by Louys et al. (2015).	
<i>Sicista praeloriger</i>	1		S	A	S	Assignment follows <i>S. subtilis</i> based on Morphological similarity (Rofes et al., 2012).	
<i>Sicista subtilis</i>			S	A	S	Assigned by Louys et al. (2015).	
<i>Spermophilus (=Citellus) sp.</i>		Kryštufek & Vohralík, 2012	S	A	S	Assignment follows <i>S. primigenius</i> and <i>S. undulatus</i> .	
<i>Spermophilus (=Citellus) citelloides</i>	1	Kryštufek & Vohralík, 2012	S	A	S	Assignment is supported by phylogenetic relationship with <i>S. suslicus</i> (Sinitsa et al., 2019).	
<i>Spermophilus (=Citellus) major</i>		Kryštufek & Vohralík, 2012	S	T	P	500-570g (Wilson et al., 2016). Phylogenetic evidence positions <i>S. major</i> between <i>S. brevicauda</i> , <i>S. erythrogegens</i> , <i>S. fulvus</i> , <i>S. suslicus</i> , and <i>S. pygmaeus</i> ; based on mitochondrial DNA sampling (Brandler et al., 2021). All genetic analogues burrow underground, and occupy open, short, arid or semi-arid grass lands, and sparsely vegetated habitats - with no explicit mention of arboreal activity or adaptation (Wilson et al., 2016). This suggests that <i>S. major</i> is more terrestrial than other species of <i>Spermophilus</i> listed here.	Herbivorous (Wilson et al., 2016).

<i>Spermophilus (=Citellus) primigenius (=citellus)</i>		Kryštufek & Vohralik, 2012	S	A	S		Assigned by Louys et al. (2015).
<i>Spermophilus (=Citellus) undulatus</i>		Kryštufek & Vohralik, 2012	S	A	S		Assigned by Louys et al. (2015).
<i>Trogotherium cuvieri</i>	1		L	T	P	Larger than the extant <i>Castor fiber</i> (Fostowicz-Frelik, 2008), which is considered >10kg (Louys et al., 2015).	<i>Trogotherium</i> in comparison with other swimming rodents indicates more cursorial locomotion (Fostowicz-Frelik, 2008). It is possible that <i>Trogotherium</i> fed on plants with wooden trunks (Fostowicz-Frelik, 2008), although microwear suggests changes in dietary composition over time (Yang et al., 2021).
<i>Acinonyx pardinensis</i>	1		L	A	S	Approximate to 100kg (Hemmer et al., 2011).	Has the similar structural and skeletal specializations as the extant cheetah, although has adaptations to an intermediate or more open habitat, and had a larger body mass (Meloro, 2007; Cherin et al., 2014; Schellhorn & Sanmugaraja, 2014). Classified as meat-eater of medium prey like the extant cheetah (Meloro, 2007; Hemmer et al., 2011; Cherin et al., 2014).
<i>Felis sp.</i>			S	A	S		Uncertain assignment based on phylogeny to <i>F. silvestris</i> .
<i>Felis chaus</i>			S	T	S		Assigned by Louys et al. (2015).
<i>Felis silvestris</i>			S	A	S		Assigned by Louys et al. (2015).
<i>Homotherium sp.</i>	1		L	T	S		Assignment follows <i>H. latidens</i> .
<i>Homotherium latidens</i>	1		L	T	S	Mass estimated up to 200kg (Serangeli et al., 2015).	Shows functional association with modern hyaena (<i>Crocota crocuta</i> ; Anyonge, 1996; Meloro, 2011) suggesting similarities in the locomotory abilities, strongly supporting an open habitat preference (Antón et al., 2005). The morphology of the dentition, head and neck are well adapted to cause rapid and extensive bleeding in animals of similar or larger size than the predator (Antón et al., 2005).
<i>Lynx sp.</i>			L	T	S		Assignment follows most common assignment to <i>Lynx</i> .

<i>Lynx (=Felis) issiodorensis</i>	1	Koufos, 2022	L	T	S	Assignment follows <i>L. lynx</i> based on Morphological similarity (Kurtén, 1978).
<i>Lynx lynx</i>			L	T	S	Assigned by Louys et al. (2015).
<i>Lynx pardinus</i>			L	T	S	7-14kg (midpoint = 10.5kg; Wilson & Mittermeier, 2009) No mention of arboreal adaptation or activity, however, appears to move terrestrially over large distances (Wilson & Mittermeier, 2009). Feeds almost exclusively on European rabbits (<i>Oryctolagus cuniculus</i>) (Wilson & Mittermeier, 2009).
<i>Lynx spelaea</i>			L	T	S	Assignment follows <i>L. pardinus</i> based on Morphological similarity (Fosse et al., 2021).
Hyenidae			L	T	S	All members assigned consistently by Louys et al. (2015).
<i>Crocuta sp.</i>			L	T	S	Assignment follows most common assignments to <i>Crocuta</i> .
<i>Crocuta crocuta</i>			L	T	S	Assigned by Louys et al. (2015).
<i>Hyaena sp.</i>			L	T	S	Assignment follows <i>Hyaena hyaena</i> (Louys et al., 2015).
<i>Pachycrocuta brevirostris</i>	1		L	T	S	Estimated as 110kg (Palmqvist et al., 2011). Displays a powerfully built body with massive and relatively short limbs, providing greater power and more stability to scavenge, dismember and carry large pieces of ungulate carcasses (Palmqvist et al., 1996; 2011). A very robust carnivore, well adapted for scavenging ungulate carcasses (Palmqvist et al., 1996; 2011).
<i>Pachycrocuta (Hyaena) prisca</i>	1		L	T	S	Assignment follows <i>Parahyaena brunnea</i> based on morphological similarity (Iannucci et al., 2021).
<i>Pliocrocuta perrieri</i>	1		L	T	S	Assignment follows <i>Parahyaena brunnea</i> based on morphological similarity (Iannucci et al., 2021).
<i>Canis sp.</i>			L	T	S	Assignment follows most common assignments to <i>Canis</i> .
<i>Canis etruscus (=olivolanus)</i>	1	Cherin et al., 2014	L	T	S	Assignment follows <i>C. lupus</i> based on phylogenetic descent (Lorenzo, 2013); although diet certainly carnivorous (Flower & Schreve, 2014).

<i>Canis ex gr. mosbachensis-arnensis</i>	1		L	T	S	Assignment follows <i>C. mosbachensis</i> .		
<i>Canis lupus</i>			L	T	S	Assigned by Louys et al. (2015).		
<i>Canis mosbachensis</i>	1		L	T	S	Assignment follows <i>C. lupus</i> based on Phylogenetic descent (Lorenzo, 2013); although diet certainly carnivorous (Flower & Schreve, 2014).		
<i>Cuon sp.</i>			L	T	S	Assignment follows most common assignment to <i>Cuon</i> .		
<i>Cuon alpinus</i>			L	T	S	Assigned by Louys et al. (2015).		
<i>Cuon priscus</i>	1		L	T	S	Assignment follows <i>C. alpinus</i> based on morphological similarity (Volmer et al., 2019; Boev 2022). Trophic habits supported by Palmqvist et al. (1996).		
<i>Cuon stehlini</i>	1		L	T	S	Assignment follows <i>C. alpinus</i> and <i>Xenocyon lycanoides</i> based on morphological similarity (Volmer et al., 2019; Boev 2022).		
<i>Xenocyon lycanoides</i>	1		L	T	S	Assignment follows <i>C. lupus</i> based on ecomorphological similarity (Palmqvist et al., 1999; Bartolini-Lucent et al., 2021).		
Lutrinae			S	T	S	Uncertain assignment, assigned based on <i>Lutra sp.</i>		
<i>Cyrnaonyx (=Lutra) antiqua</i>	1	van Bree et al., 1999	S	T	S	7.8-10.8kg (midpoint = 9.3kg; Mecozzi et al., 2021).	<i>Cyrnaonyx</i> shows adaptations like <i>Lutra</i> and probably was a stream dweller (Willemsen, 1992).	We may assume that <i>C. antiqua</i> also descended from a species feeding on fast-moving prey (Willemsen, 1992).
<i>Gulo gulo</i>			L	A	S	Assigned by Louys et al. (2015).		
<i>Gulo schlosseri</i>	1		L	A	S	Assignment follows <i>G. gulo</i> based on morphological similarity (Krajcarz, 2012; Samuels et al., 2018).		
<i>Lutra sp.</i>			S	T	S	Assignment follows most common assignments to <i>Lutra</i> .		
<i>Lutra lutra</i>			S	T	S	Assigned by Louys et al. (2015).		
<i>Martes sp.</i>			S	A	S	Assignment follows most common assignments to <i>Martes</i> .		
<i>Martes martes</i>			S	A	S	Assigned by Louys et al. (2015).		

<i>Meles sp.</i>		L	T	S	Assignment follows most common assignment to <i>Meles</i> .
<i>Meles atavus</i>	1	L	T	S	Assignment follows <i>M. meles</i> based on morphological similarity (Savvidou et al., 2022).
<i>Meles meles</i>		L	T	S	Assigned by Louys et al. (2015).
<i>Meles thoralis</i>	1	L	T	S	Assignment follows <i>M. meles</i> based on morphological similarity (Savvidou et al., 2022).
<i>Mustela sp.</i>		S	A	S	Assignment follows most common assignments to <i>Mustela</i> .
<i>Mustela erminea</i>		S	A	S	Assigned by Louys et al. (2015).
<i>Mustela eversmannii</i>		S	A	S	Assigned by Louys et al. (2015).
<i>Mustela lutreola</i>		S	A	S	Assigned by Louys et al. (2015).
<i>Mustela nivalis</i>		S	A	S	Assigned by Louys et al. (2015).
<i>Mustela palerminea</i>	1	S	A	S	Assignment follows <i>Mu. erminea</i> based on phylogenetic similarity (Marciszak et al., 2021).
<i>Mustela praenivalis</i>	1	S	A	S	Assignment follows <i>Mu. nivalis</i> based on phylogenetic similarity (Marciszak et al., 2021).
<i>Mustela putorius</i>		S	A	S	Assigned by Louys et al. (2015).
<i>Mustela putorius stromeri</i>	1	S	A	S	Assignment follows <i>Mu. Eversmannii</i> based on morphological and phylogenetic similarity (Sato et al., 2003; Gimranov et al., 2023).
<i>Panthera sp.</i>		L	A	S	Assignment follows most common assignments to <i>Panthera</i> .
<i>Panthera gombaszogensis</i>	1	L	T	S	Approximated as 140kg (Argant & Argant, 2011). The supposition that <i>P. gombaszogensis</i> is most closely related to the jaguar and thus should mirror its ecomorphology is not supported (O'Regan, 2002). It shows evidence of cursorial adaptation, <i>P. Gombaszoegensis</i> is a carnivore, thought to have competed for prey with modern leopards (O'Regan, 2002).

indicative of open habitat specialisation (Meloro, 2011), with no clear association with forested environments (O'Regan, 2002).

There is however association with other species assigned as terrestrial, namely *Homotherium* and *Pachycrocuta brevirostris* (O'Regan, 2002).

<i>Panthera leo</i>		L	A	S		Assigned by Louys et al. (2015).
<i>Panthera pardus</i>		L	A	S		Assigned by Louys et al. (2015).
<i>Ursus sp.</i>		L	A	S		Assignment follows most common assignments to <i>Ursus</i> here and in Louys et al. (2015).
<i>Ursus arctos</i>		L	T	S		Assigned by Louys et al. (2015).
<i>Ursus ex gr. deningeri-spelaea</i>	1	L	A	S		Assignment follows <i>Ursus sp.</i>
<i>Ursus deningeri</i>	1	L	A	S	Reconstructed as 250kg (Veitschegger, 2017).	<i>Ursus deningeri</i> appears scansorial (Meloro & Oliveira, 2019). Deninger's bears align with other herbivorous bears, although isotope results, suggest that <i>U. deningeri</i> was highly omnivorous (van Heteren et al., 2018).
<i>Ursus spelaeus</i>	1	L	T	S	Comparable to the largest extant ursids, with females spanning 225-259kg, and males spanning 400-500kg, with large specimens spanning 700-800kg, or even up to a tonne (Christiansen, 1999).	In the majority of cases, fossil brown bears and cave bears are consistently categorized like the polar bear as lacking the ability of climbing and adapted to open habitats (Meloro & Oliveira, 2019). It is not appropriate to view Late Pleistocene cave bears as strictly or even predominantly vegetarian but as flexible omnivores within their diverse communities (Robu et al., 2013; Ramírez-Pedraza et al., 2020).
<i>Ursus thibetanus (=stehlini)</i>		L	A	S	Baryshnikov, 2010	Assigned by Louys et al. (2015).

<i>Vulpes sp.</i>			S	T	S		Assignment follows <i>V. vulpes</i> .
<i>Alopex (Vulpes) sp.</i>			S	T	S		Assignment follows <i>A. lagopus</i> .
<i>Vulpes sp. or Alopex (Vulpes) sp.</i>			S	T	S		Assignment follows <i>Vulpes sp.</i> and <i>Alopex (Vulpes) sp.</i>
<i>Alopex (=Vulpes) lagopus</i>		Norén et al., 2023	S	T	S		Assigned by Louys et al. (2015).
<i>Vulpes praeglacialis</i>	1		S	T	S		Assignment follows <i>V. vulpes</i> based on similarity outlined by Lucenti & Madurell-Malapeira (2020); with support for dietary assignment by Palmqvist et al. (1996; 2003)
<i>Vulpes vulpes</i>			S	T	S		Assigned by Louys et al. (2015).
Elephantidae			L	T	P		Consistent functional group from all members listed here.
<i>Elaphas sp.</i>			L	T	P		Assignment follows <i>E. maximus</i> .
<i>Mammuthus sp.</i>			L	T	P		Assignment follows most common assignments to <i>Mammuthus</i> here.
<i>Mammuthus ex gr. primigenius-trogontherii</i>	1		L	T	P	Members of the genus unanimously weigh numerous tonnes (Larramendi, 2015).	<i>Mammuthus</i> appear to favour open steppe and tundra habitats, void of arboreal habitat (Guthrie, 1982; Kubiak, 1982). Furthermore, mammoth migrations highlight terrestrial locomotion over vast distance (Hoppe, 2004). The transitional form between <i>M. trogontherii</i> and <i>M. primigenius</i> has microwear patterns that correspond to grass-dominated mixed feeders (Rivals et al., 2019).
<i>Mammuthus (=Elephas) primigenius</i>	1	Athanassiou, 2022	L	T	P	Approximate to 3,900kg in Siberia and 6,900kg in Western Europe (Larramendi, 2015).	<i>Mammuthus</i> appear to favour open steppe and tundra habitats, void of arboreal habitat (Guthrie, 1982; Kubiak, 1982). Furthermore, mammoth migrations highlight terrestrial locomotion over vast distance (Hoppe, 2004). Dental wear patterns from eight samples of <i>M. primigenius</i> mostly compare with extant grazers (Rivals et al., 2019). Exceptions include grass-dominated mixed feeders, leaf browsers, or browse-dominated mixed feeders (Rivals et al., 2019).
<i>Mammuthus trogontherii</i>	1		L	T	P	Greater than 10,000kg (Larramendi, 2015).	<i>Mammuthus</i> appear to favour open steppe and tundra habitats, void of arboreal habitat (Guthrie, 1982; Kubiak, 1982). The microwear indicates dietary traits that cover the mixed feeding and grazing (Rivals et al., 2019). Absence

							1982; Kubiak, 1982). Furthermore, mammoth migrations highlight terrestrial locomotion over vast distance (Hoppe, 2004).	of puncture pits are absent suggesting that it did not feed on any fruit resources (Rivals et al., 2019). The presence of significant numbers of wide scratches suggests some consumption of bark and/or twigs of trees and bushes (Rivals et al., 2019).
<i>Palaeoloxodon (=Elephas) antiquus</i>	1	Athanassiou, 2022	L	T	P	Greater than 10,000kg (Larramendi, 2015).	Larramendi & Palombo (2015) investigated the locomotory adaptations from the neighbouring taxa <i>P. falconeri</i> ; which are more cursorial than all extant elephants: all of which are considered terrestrial (Louys et al., 2015). This is supported by young <i>P. antiquus</i> (Larramendi & Palombo, 2015). Tracks of newborn <i>P. antiquus</i> indicate terrestrial locomotion (Neto de Carvalho et al., 2021).	<i>Palaeoloxodon antiquus</i> shows significant dietary plasticity with browsing, grazing and mixed feeding patterns observed (Rivals et al., 2019).
Rhinocerotidae			L	T	P	Consistent functional group from all members listed here.		
<i>Coelodonta antiquitatis</i>	1		L	T	P	Estimates differ between 1500kg (Boeskorov, 2012) and 2400kg (Mallet et al., 2022).	Morphology changes between two chronosubspecies: <i>C. a. praecursor</i> (Middle Pleistocene) and <i>C. a. antiquitatis</i> (Late Pleistocene) highlighting change from cursorial to fully graviportal locomotor adaptations (Uzunidis et al., 2022).	Isotopic analysis shows that <i>Coelodonta antiquitatis</i> was a grazer in localities from glacial, interglacial and interstadial periods, with the capacity to adapt its diet to the season and vegetation (Stefaniak et al., 2021).
<i>Pliorhinus (=Stephanorhinus) megarhinus</i>	1	Pandolfi et al., 2021	L	T	P	Estimates range between 2079-3223kg (Pandolfi et al., 2025).	<i>Pliorhinus</i> forms a clade with <i>Coelodonta</i> (Pandolfi, 2023) and is assigned locomotory grouping assigned to the only species of <i>Coelodonta</i> examined here: <i>C. antiquitatis</i> .	Morphology, mesowear, and microwear position this species between modern browser species (Ballatore, 2016).

<i>Dicerorhinus sp.</i>			L	T	P	Assignment follows most common assignments to <i>Stephanorhinus</i> .		
<i>Stephanorhinus sp.</i>	1		L	T	P	Assignment follows most common assignments to <i>Stephanorhinus</i> .		
<i>Stephanorhinus (=Dicerorhinus) etruscus</i>	1	Persico et al., 2015	L	T	P	No direct size estimates available, so assumed to be in the proximity of 1,500kg based on other taxa in the genus.	Limb, dentition, and head posture of suggest adaptation to browse vegetation of intermediate height in open habitats (García-Fernández et al., 2023), suggesting terrestrial locomotion.	Mesowear and microwear both indicate that <i>S. etruscus</i> had dominant browsing habits (Rivals & Lister, 2016).
<i>Stephanorhinus (=Dicerorhinus) hemitoechus</i>	1	Persico et al., 2015	L	T	P	1,561kg (Mallet et al., 2021).	Shows remarkable similarity to <i>Coelodonta antiquitatis</i> (Fortelius et al., 1993), which has a high degree of graviportal locomotion (Uzunidis et al., 2022).	Dental morphology and mesowear suggests shifts between mixed feeder to consuming more grass when necessary (Van Asperen & Kahlke, 2015).
<i>Stephanorhinus hundsheimensis</i>	1		L	T	P	1,348kg (Mallet et al., 2021).	Limb, dentition, and head posture of suggest adaptation to browse vegetation of intermediate height in open habitats (García-Fernández et al., 2023), suggesting terrestrial locomotion.	Dental wear patterns show two extant dietary analogues: <i>Dicerorhinus sumatrensis</i> and <i>Redunca redunca</i> (Kahlke & Kaiser, 2011) - both of which are primary consumers (Louys et al., 2015).
<i>Stephanorhinus (=Dicerorhinus) kirchbergensis</i>	1	Persico et al., 2015	L	T	P	1811-1941kg (Saarinen et al., 2016).	Relatively cursorial, with joint surfaces of the limbs suggesting a forest or woodland environment (Fortelius et al., 1993).	Isotopic analysis (Stefaniak et al., 2021) and morphological/mesowear analysis (Van Asperen & Kahlke, 2015) supports mixed feeder.
Equidae			L	T	P	Assignment follows <i>Equus sp.</i>		
<i>Equus sp.</i>			L	T	P	Assigned >10kg following all other members of the genus.	The evolution of equids over the past ~25mya in both tridactyl and monodactyl forms are adapted to terrestrial locomotor types (Kaashoek et al., 2023).	All extant <i>Equus</i> exhibit primary consumer diets (Louys et al., 2015) - this is also observed through palaeodiet reconstructions from the late pleistocene (Rivals et al., 2015) and middle pleistocene (Uzunidis, 2021).

<i>Equus altidens</i>		L	T	P	Assignment follows Equus sp.
<i>Equus caballus</i>		L	T	P	Assigned by Louys et al. (2015).
<i>Equus chosaricus</i>		L	T	P	Assignment follows Equus sp.
<i>Equus ferus</i>		L	T	P	Assignment follows Equus sp.
<i>Equus germanicus</i>		L	T	P	Assignment follows Equus sp.
<i>Equus mosbachensis-taubachensis</i>		L	T	P	Assignment follows Equus sp.
<i>Equus hydruntinus</i>		L	T	P	Assignment follows Equus sp.
<i>Equus mosbachensis</i>		L	T	P	Assignment follows Equus sp.
<i>Equus przewalskii</i>		L	T	P	Assignment follows Equus sp.
<i>Equus remagensis</i>		L	T	P	Assignment follows Equus sp.
<i>Equus steinheimensis</i>		L	T	P	Assignment follows Equus sp.
<i>Equus taubachensis</i>		L	T	P	Assignment follows Equus sp.
<i>Alces sp.</i>		L	T	P	Assignment follows <i>A. alces</i> .
<i>Alces alces (=palmatus)</i>	Breda & Marchetti, 2005	L	T	P	Assigned by Louys et al. (2015).
Bovidae		L	T	P	Consistent functional group from all members listed here.
<i>Bos sp. or Bison sp.</i>		L	T	P	Assignment follows most common assignments <i>Bos</i> and <i>Bison</i> .
<i>Bos sp.</i>		L	T	P	Assignment follows <i>B. primigenius</i> .

<i>Bos primigenius</i>	1	L	T	P	Mass comparable to a wisent (<i>Bison bonasus</i>) or the banteng (<i>Bos javanicus</i> ; Van Vuure, 2014), both of which assigned by Louys et al. (2015).	Limbs are typical of 'low-gear' locomotion, used to increase stability, especially on rocky and uneven grounds, and often in a carnivore-free environment (Siarabi et al., 2023).	Mesowear indicates mixed-feeding diets with a significant component of grass (Saarinen et al., 2016).
<i>Bison sp.</i>		L	T	P	Assignment follows most common assignments to <i>Bison</i> .		
<i>Bison bonasus</i>		L	T	P	Assigned by Louys et al. (2015).		
<i>Bison priscus</i>	1	L	T	P	Mass of up to 1,000kg (Boeskorov et al., 2016).	Distal limbs indicate that early and middle Pleistocene European <i>Bison</i> were generally cursorial (Maniakas & Kostopoulos, 2017).	Mesowear indicates mixed-feeding diets with a significant component of grass (Saarinen et al., 2016).
<i>Bison schoetensacki</i>	1	L	T	P	Similar size to <i>B. priscus</i> (Palacio et al., 2017).	Distal limbs indicate that early and middle Pleistocene European <i>Bison</i> were generally cursorial (Maniakas & Kostopoulos, 2017).	Mesowear indicates mixed-feeding diets with a significant component of grass (Saarinen et al., 2016).
<i>Bubalus murrensis</i>	1	L	T	P	No complete skeleton has been found (Vislobokova et al., 2021), so size will follow the other extant members of <i>Bubalus</i> (Louys et al., 2015).	Closest extant relative (<i>Bubalus arnee</i> (= <i>bubalis</i>); synonym provided by Gentry et al. (2004)) suggests locomotion suited to similar habitats (swamps, muddy banks, and water bodies; Van Dam et al., 1997), and similar browser diet (Vislobokova et al., 2021).	
<i>Capra sp. or Rupicapra sp.</i>		L	T	P	Assignment follows most common assignments to <i>Rupicapra</i> and <i>Capra</i> .		
<i>Capra sp.</i>		L	T	P	Assignment follows most common assignments to <i>Capra</i> .		
<i>Capra caucasica</i>		L	T	P	Assigned by Louys et al. (2015).		
<i>Capra ibex</i>		L	T	P	Assigned by Louys et al. (2015).		
<i>Rupicapra sp.</i>		L	T	P	Assignment follows most common assignments to <i>Rupicapra</i> .		

<i>Rupicapra pyrenaica</i>			L	T	P		Assigned by Louys et al. (2015).
<i>Rupicapra rupicapra</i>			L	T	P		Assigned by Louys et al. (2015).
Cervidae			L	T	P		Consistent functional group from all members listed here.
<i>Capreolus sp.</i>			L	T	P		Assignment follows <i>C. capreolus-sussenbornensis</i> .
<i>Capreolus capreolus-sussenbornensis</i>			L	T	P		<i>C. capreolus</i> assigned by Louys et al. (2015). <i>C. sussenbornensis</i> is an extinct taxon, up to 25% larger than <i>C. capreolus</i> , but morphologically similar (Pfeiffer, 1998).
<i>Cervalces (=Alces) latifrons</i>	1	Stefaniak et al., 2014	L	T	P	Approximately 1000kg (Boeskorov, 2005).	Similar dental and postcranial <i>Alces</i> and <i>Cervalces</i> suggests that the extinct genus could have chewed the same kind of food and moved in the same way as extant <i>Alces</i> (Breda et al., 2005) - terrestrial primary consumers assigned by Louys et al., (2015).
<i>Cervus sp.</i>			L	T	P		Assignment follows most common assignments to <i>Cervus</i> .
<i>Cervus elaphus</i>		<i>C. elaphus</i> has included <i>C. simplicidens</i> occurrences due to recent evidence that the two species should be integrated (Croitor, 2020).	L	T	P		Assigned by Louys et al. (2015).
<i>Cervus reichenau</i> (=elaphoides)	1	Pfeiffer-Deml, 2018	L	T	P	ca. 120kg (Croiter et al., 2018).	The dental and antler morphology indicate phyletic relationship with <i>H. mediterraneus</i> indicating terrestrial, primary consumer adaptation (Croitor et al., 2018).
<i>Dama sp.</i>			L	T	P		Assignment follows <i>D. dama</i> .
<i>Dama dama</i>			L	T	P		Assigned by Louys et al. (2015).
<i>Dama clactoniana</i>	1		L	T	P		Assignment follows <i>D. dama</i> based on morphological similarity (Mecozzi et al., 2024).
<i>Haploidoceros (=Euctenoceros) mediterraneus</i>	1	Croitor et al., 2018	L	T	P	ca. 70-80kg (Croiter et al., 2018).	Antler morphology shared by <i>Bison</i> and <i>Rangifer tarandus</i> , and general adaptations reflect 'Dama-like' deer niche (Croitor et al., 2018). All comparisons indicate terrestrial Dental morphology indicates a browsing/mixed feeding habit (Croitor et al., 2018).

							locomotion (Louys et al., 2015).
<i>Hemitragus bonali</i>	1		L	T	P	ca. 96kg (Rodríguez-Gómez et al., 2024).	Robust metapodials and relatively short metacarpals, reflects the most advanced grade of adaptation to mountainous habitats (Van der Made et al., 2008). This may facilitate the climbing of rocky terrain but is not sufficient to suggest that this taxon has any arboreal tendency. Mesowear suggests mixed feeder or grazing diet, but the microwear signal is more typical of an extant grazer (Rivals et al., 2008).
<i>Hemitragus cedrensis</i>	1		L	T	P		<i>Hemitragus cedrensis</i> has morphological features intermediate between <i>H. bonali</i> and <i>H. jemlabicus</i> (Crégut-Bonnoure, 1989; Rivals & Blasco, 2008), so functional group has been assigned from <i>H. bonali</i> .
<i>Hippopotamus amphibius</i>		<i>Hippopotamus incognitus</i> is considered an invalid species by Petronio (1995), and Fidalgo et al. (2024), thus assigned here.	L	T	P		Assigned by Louys et al. (2015).
<i>Hippopotamus antiquus</i>	1		L	T	P	Estimates between 1012-3260kg (Martino et al., 2025).	Shorter metapodials indicate not well designed for dwelling outside of aquatic habitats (Palmqvist et al., 2008) suggesting locomotion far from arboreal. High $\delta^{15}N$ values obtained from remains suggest a diet predominantly of aquatic plants (Palmqvist et al., 2008).
<i>Megaloceros sp.</i>	1		L	T	P		Assignment follows <i>M. giganteus</i> .
<i>Megaloceros (=Megaceros) giganteus</i>	1	Lister, 1987	L	T	P	ca. 687kg (Saarinen et al., 2016).	Head movements optimised for grazing (Shpansky, 2014), maintains open-landscape adaptation features such as the cursorial adapted limbs (Croiter, 2021). Mesowear and microwear indicate a diet ranging from grazing to browse-dominated mixed-feeding (Rivals & Lister, 2016).
<i>Ovibos moschatus</i>			L	T	P		Assigned by Louys et al. (2015).
<i>Ovis ammon</i>			L	T	P		Assigned by Louys et al. (2015).
<i>Praemegaceros dawkinsi</i>	1		L	T	P	ca. 220kg (Croiter et al., 2018).	Assignment follows <i>M. giganteus</i> and <i>P. verticornis</i> based on morphological similarity; and <i>P. verticornis</i> based on phylogenetic proximity (Vislobokova, 2013).

<i>Praemegaceros solilhacus</i>	1	L	T	P		Assignment follows <i>P. dawkinsi</i> and <i>P. verticornis</i> based on phylogenetic proximity (Vislobokova, 2013).
<i>Praemegaceros verticornis</i>	1	L	T	P	Larger than <i>P. dawkinsi</i> (Vislobokova, 2013).	Limb morphology supports adaptation to firm ground (Vislobokova, 2013). Dental morphology adapted for grinding of coarse food (proposed dietary source includes a significant proportion of herbs) (Vislobokova, 2013).
<i>Praeovibos priscus</i>	1	L	T	P	ca. 327kg (Meloro et al., 2007).	Assignment is taken from Louys et al.'s (2015) assignment of <i>Ovibos moschatus</i> because of morphological and phylogenetic similarity (Campos et al., 2010). Mesowear reflects mixed feeder or grazer diet; microwear supports grazer (Rivals et al., 2008).
<i>Rangifer sp.</i>		L	T	P		Assignment follows <i>R. tarandus</i> .
<i>Rangifer tarandus</i>		L	T	P		Assigned by Louys et al. (2015).
<i>Sus sp.</i>		L	T	S		Assignment follows <i>S. scrofa</i> .
<i>Sus scrofa</i>		L	T	S		Assigned by Louys et al. (2015).

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